

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Carvalho, L. P., & Rodrigues, A. P. G. (2025). Dangerous contexts: An analysis of leadership perception in special police operations. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 29(4), e240276. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2025240276.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Carvalho, L. P., & Rodrigues, A. P. G., Rezende, G. M., & Stéfani, S. R. (2025). Peer review report for: Dangerous contexts: An analysis of leadership perception in special police operations. RAC. Revista de Administração Contemporânea. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16316442>

REVIEWERS:

- Gustavo Matarazzo Rezende (Instituto Federal de Educação Ciência e Tecnologia de São Paulo, Brazil)
- Silvio Roberto Stéfani (Universidade Estadual do Centro-Oeste, Brazil)

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Gustavo Matarazzo Rezende
Date review returned: November 05, 2024
Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

Thank you for the opportunity to review this manuscript titled "DANGEROUS CONTEXTS: AN ANALYSIS OF LEADERSHIP PERCEPTION IN SPECIAL POLICE OPERATIONS." The manuscript is engaging, has a clear

objective, and is logically structured. Additionally, it addresses a significant phenomenon, namely the perception of leadership in special police operations, which is especially relevant in the context of violence in Brazil. However, several issues should be addressed before the manuscript can be considered for publication. I outline my concerns below:

1. After reading the manuscript, I found myself questioning the limitations of studying leadership solely from the perspective of leaders. It would be beneficial to discuss these limitations and potential opportunities in the Introduction section.
2. The concept of "crisis events" is central to your analysis. I suggest further developing this category within the context of police literature.
3. Given that BOPE and the Brazilian context are relevant to this study, it would be helpful to include a paragraph on BOPE and the Brazilian context. Currently, the manuscript primarily draws on American perspectives.
4. Regarding your literature review, many of your references are over ten years old. It's important to update. This section could be better organized, and it would be valuable to provide a more systematic overview of the literature on leadership in dangerous contexts.
5. While your analysis of results is strong, I recommend organizing it by thematic sections (e.g., trust, attributes for building trust, decision-making, teamwork, moral values such as duty and fraternity). Clearly marking these divisions within the paragraphs would enhance readability.

I believe your paper has significant potential, and I hope my comments will support its further development.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).:

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Good

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Silvio Roberto Stéfani

Date review returned: November 20, 2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Congratulations on developing the article on such an important tema.

Introduction: make clear what the problem or research question and main purpose.

Literature review: include international articles from the last 3 years related to the topic with recent studies.

Methodology: present the analysis categories and authors, as well as the approval by the ethics committee.

Results: create a results matrix with the categories, the main research findings and content analysis.

Conclusions: present the practical and theoretical implications of the study and the research agenda.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Good

Originality: Excellent

Overall: Good

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Dear Reviewers,

We sincerely appreciate your careful attention and valuable contributions to our research. We have reviewed all your suggestions and made every effort to address them.

The following table outlines each suggestion and our respective responses.

All changes made to the manuscript, in line with your suggestions, are highlighted in yellow. Additionally, we have included an epigraph in the introduction, featuring one of the interviewees' accounts, to provide readers with an initial impression of the emotional depth of our findings.

Thank you.

Comments:

Reviewer: 1

Reviewer 1	Authors' response
<p>1. After reading the manuscript, I found myself questioning the limitations of studying leadership solely from the perspective of leaders. It would be beneficial to discuss these limitations and potential opportunities in the Introduction section.</p>	<p>We agree with the relevance of this topic; however, we chose to address it not in the introduction but in the final considerations as part of the research agenda. This decision was made because the introduction focuses on the problematization of the research topic and includes a paragraph that makes clear the problem question and main purpose, as recommended by Reviewer 2.</p> <p>To address the limitations of studying leadership solely from the perspective of leaders, we expanded one paragraph and created another in the final considerations. These additions highlight as future research suggestions the analysis of the phenomenon of leadership in dangerous contexts from the perception of subordinates, as well as the dilemma between military hierarchy and discipline.</p>
<p>2. The concept of "crisis events" is central to your analysis. I suggest further developing this category within the context of police literature.</p>	<p>To address this suggestion, we have incorporated the concept of 'crisis' as defined by Brazilian military police organizations into the second paragraph of the literature review. These definitions are formally established in the official documents of these institutions. This addition strengthens the theoretical foundation of the study by contextualizing crisis events within the framework of police operations, thereby aligning the analysis with the realities of high-risk scenarios faced by these organizations.</p>
<p>3. Given that BOPE and the Brazilian context are relevant to this study, it would be helpful to include a paragraph on BOPE and the Brazilian context. Currently, the manuscript primarily draws on American perspectives.</p> <p>(tradução): Dado que o BOPE e o contexto brasileiro são relevantes para este estudo, seria útil incluir um parágrafo sobre o BOPE e o contexto brasileiro. Atualmente, o manuscrito baseia-se principalmente em perspectivas americanas.</p>	<p>The Brazilian context and BOPE are already addressed in the first two paragraphs of the introduction. To further strengthen this aspect, we have expanded the second paragraph of the literature review to include, in addition to the concept of crisis as defined by military police organizations, the expertise of BOPE in managing such crises. Additionally, we have included data highlighting the challenges for a military police officer to join BOPE, such as the rigorous selection process with a 90% rejection rate, and the distinction of becoming a 'Caveira' (as they are known). These enhancements emphasize the specialized nature of BOPE's operations and reinforce the contextual relevance of the study.</p> <p>To emphasize the Brazilian context over American perspectives, we developed the fifth paragraph of the introduction using data from the Brazilian Public Security Forum (2023).</p>

(continue)

Authors' Responses (continuation)

Reviewer 1	Authors' response
<p>4. Regarding your literature review, many of your references are over ten years old. It's importante to update. This section could be better organized, and it would be valuable to provide a more systematic overview of the literature on leadership in dangerous contexts.</p>	<p>The use of more recent literature is an important observation, also highlighted by Reviewer 2. For the development of this study, the authors conducted an integrative review (published in 2023) to investigate the state of the art of the phenomenon of Leadership in police work applied to critical contexts.</p> <p>This integrative review is cited in the article's references (lines 52–56, p. 16) to support the introduction paragraph (lines 16–22, p. 3), which states that the topic of police leadership in dangerous contexts remains relatively underexplored within the realm of police organizations, particularly concerning extreme situations with non-routine and non-standard demands.</p> <p>To address the reviewers' suggestion, we conducted a systematic search, replicating the steps of the integrative review but with criteria focused on peer-reviewed articles published in the last five years, using the simplified query (Leadership AND ("law enforcement" OR police) AND ("dangerous context")). The databases Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), and Scielo did not yield any new results. Complementarily, we applied the same criteria to specialized journals, such as Police Quarterly and Police Journal from Sage Journals, Military Psychology and Police Practice and Research from Taylor & Francis, and Brazilian journals like Cadernos de Segurança Pública, Revista Brasileira de Estudos de Segurança Pública, and Revista Ciência & Polícia, but no relevant results were found.</p> <p>Thus, it is worth mentioning that the systematic search and the absence of recent publications reinforce the literature gap regarding the exploration of the topic leadership in dangerous contexts and the originality of this article's proposal in addressing a topic that remains underexplored in police organizations.</p>
<p>5. While your analysis of results is strong, I recommend organizing it by thematic sections (e.g., trust, attributes for building trust, decision-making, teamwork, moral values such as duty and fraternity). Clearly marking these divisions within the paragraphs would enhance readability.</p>	<p>Thank you for this valuable suggestion. In response, we organized the results section into thematic divisions, marking these distinctions clearly within the paragraphs. This adjustment has indeed improved both the visual presentation and the flow of the article. We greatly appreciate your recommendation, as it has significantly enhanced the readability and overall coherence of the manuscript.</p>

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Reviewer: 2

Reviewer 2	Authors' response
<p>Introduction: make clear what the problem or research question and main purpose.</p>	<p>To address the reviewer's suggestion, we have added information to the final paragraph of the introduction to clarify the research problem and main purpose. Specifically, we emphasized the need to understand how leadership is practiced in dangerous contexts, highlighting its critical role in preserving lives and ensuring the physical and moral integrity of all parties involved in high-risk situations.</p> <p>We also detailed the study's objective, which focuses on analyzing the perceptions of current and former commanders of the Special Police Operations Battalion (BOPE) regarding their leadership practices during dangerous and volatile situations. These additions aim to provide a clearer connection between the research problem and its purpose, aligning with the reviewer's recommendation.</p>
<p>Literature review: include international articles from the last 3 years related to the topic with recent studies.</p>	<p>The use of more recent literature is an important observation, also highlighted by Reviewer 1. For the development of this study, the authors conducted an integrative review (published in 2023) to investigate the state of the art of the phenomenon of Leadership in police work applied to critical contexts.</p> <p>This integrative review is cited in the article's references (lines 52–56, p. 16) to support the introduction paragraph (lines 16–22, p. 3), which states that the topic of police leadership in dangerous contexts remains relatively underexplored within the realm of police organizations, particularly concerning extreme situations with non-routine and non-standard demands.</p> <p>To address the reviewers' suggestion, we conducted a systematic search, replicating the steps of the integrative review but with criteria focused on peer-reviewed articles published in the last five years, using the simplified query (Leadership AND ("law enforcement" OR police) AND ("dangerous context")). The databases Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), and Scielo did not yield any new results. Complementarily, we applied the same criteria to specialized journals, such as Police Quarterly and Police Journal from Sage Journals, Military Psychology and Police Practice and Research from Taylor & Francis, and Brazilian journals like Cadernos de Segurança Pública, Revista Brasileira de Estudos de Segurança Pública, and Revista Ciência & Polícia, but no relevant results were found.</p> <p>Thus, it is worth mentioning that the systematic search and the absence of recent publications reinforce the literature gap regarding the exploration of the topic leadership in dangerous contexts and the originality of this article's proposal in addressing a topic that remains underexplored in police organizations.</p>

(continue)

Authors' Responses (continuation)

Reviewer 1	Authors' response
<p>Methodology: present the analysis categories and authors, as well as the approval by the ethics committee.</p>	<p>- We included in the paragraph immediately after Figure 1 the information that the research was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Santa Catarina State University (UDESC) under substantiated opinion number 6.220.807, issued on August 4, 2023.</p> <p>- Thematic analysis, as outlined by Braun and Clarke, was adopted to examine and structure the qualitative data. The phases of thematic analysis are clearly presented in Table 1. In thematic analysis, we refer to the grouping of codes (patterns) as themes rather than categories, although they share similarities. Accordingly, the themes (categories) are highlighted in the thematic map (Figure 2) and Table 2. To enhance clarity and emphasize these themes, we added a column with the definitions of each theme in Table 2.</p>
<p>Results: create a results matrix with the categories, the main research findings and content analysis.</p>	<p>As mentioned in our previous response, thematic analysis, as outlined by Braun and Clarke, was adopted to examine and structure the qualitative data. In thematic analysis, we refer to the grouping of codes (patterns) as themes rather than categories. Accordingly, the themes (categories) are highlighted in the thematic map (Figure 2) and Table 2.</p> <p>In response to the suggestion to create a results matrix for clarity, we added a column with the definitions of each theme in Table 2. This addition provides a clear representation of the themes and their definitions, reflecting the main findings of the research.</p>
<p>Conclusions: present the practical and theoretical implications of the study and the research agenda.</p>	<p>In response, we have expanded the final considerations to include these implications. Theoretically, the study shifts the focus from influence to trust as the central element of leadership effectiveness in high-risk contexts. Practically, it emphasizes the importance of leaders fostering strong, consistent trust within their teams to ensure success in life-threatening situations. Additionally, we stress the need for public security institutions to prioritize psychological and operational preparation for both leaders and subordinates.</p> <p>To address the suggestion of presenting a research agenda in the conclusions, we have expanded the final considerations to include reflections on the dilemma between military hierarchy and discipline. Furthermore, we have highlighted the analysis of leadership in dangerous contexts from the perspective of subordinates.</p>

ROUND 2**Reviewer 1 report**

Reviewer: Gustavo Matarazzo Rezende
Date review returned: December 09, 2024
Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the Author

Dear Authors,

I would like to congratulate you on the work done. The suggestions provided in the previous round were incorporated with great rigor and quality, and the arguments presented for those that were not fully adopted were well-founded and clear.

Thank you for the opportunity to collaborate in the review of this article and for the enriching exchanges throughout the process. I wish you success in the continuation of this work and in your future publications.

Best regards

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).:

Rating:

Interest: Excellent

Quality: Good

Originality: Excellent

Overall: Good

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Silvio Roberto Stéfani

Date review returned: December 30, 2024

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the Author

The authors have performed the requested revisions. The paper can be approved.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Rating:

Interest: Excellent

Quality: Good

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Authors' Responses

There was no author's response from the reviewers for this round